

JEL: C23, O21, Q18

Anatolii Kulyk¹, Katerina Fokina-Mezentseva², Oksana Piankova²,

Maryna Slokva², Liudmyla Sierova²

¹Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman

²Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics

MODELING OF CEREAL AND LEGUME YIELD ON THE BASIS OF AGRO- AND METEO-FACTORS USING REGULARIZED REGRESSION METHODS

Purpose. The purpose of the study is to model the yield of grain and legume crops in the Odessa region based on a complex of agro- and meteorological factors using regularized regression methods (Ridge, Lasso, ElasticNet).

Methodology / approach. The article applies economic and mathematical analysis using official statistics for 1995–2024. 11 independent variables were selected for modeling, reflecting agro-technological and climatic factors. The assessment was carried out using classical linear regression and its regularized modifications. Multicollinearity diagnostics, cross-validation, and analysis of statistical significance of coefficients were performed.

Results. It is shown that models with regularization provide higher accuracy of yield forecasting compared to classical regression. The best results were demonstrated by Ridge regression ($R^2 = 0.606$; $RMSE = 4.46$), which revealed key positive factors: crop area, rainfall, application of mineral fertilizers and pesticides, hydrothermal coefficient. The deficit of air saturation with moisture and wind speed had a negative impact on yield.

Originality / scientific novelty. The scientific novelty lies in the combination of agronomic and meteorological indicators within the framework of regularized models, which allows taking into account multicollinearity and at the same time identifying the most significant yield factors. The results obtained deepen knowledge about the relationships between agrotechnological and climatic factors in the conditions of the Southern Steppe of Ukraine.

Practical value / implications. The results of the study can be used by agricultural enterprises and management bodies to optimize fertilizer systems, plan crop areas, select adaptive varieties, and increase the resilience of agricultural production to climate risks. The proposed models provide tools for predicting yields and making management decisions in the field of agro-economics.

Key words: agro-economic modeling, yield forecasting, Ridge-, Lasso-, ElasticNet- regression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring a stable and high level of crop yields is one of the key tasks of modern agricultural production, especially in the context of climate change and increasing pressure on natural resources. Cereals and legumes are the basis of food security in most countries in the world, therefore, the study of factors determining their yield is of both scientific and practical importance.

Yield is a complex function of many interrelated factors, among which agrofactors (the amount of applied mineral and organic fertilizers, the use of plant protection products) and meteorological factors (average air temperature, soil surface temperature, wind speed, number of days with precipitation, etc.) play an important role. Understanding the impact of these variables on the final agricultural result allows you to optimize the farming system, increase the efficiency of agrotechnical measures and ensure adaptive planning in conditions of climatic fluctuations.

This study focuses on the use of regression analysis methods, in particular linear regression and its regularized modifications - Ridge, Lasso and ElasticNet. These methods allow not only to build predictive yield models, but also to isolate the most significant influencing factors, reducing the risk of over-calculating the model by controlling complexity. Regularized methods are especially useful when there is a large number of correlated predictors, which is typical for agrometeorological data.

The aim of the article is to model the yield of grain and legume crops based on a complex of agro- and meteorological factors using regularized regression methods. The paper investigates the influence of these factors on yield and assesses the accuracy of the constructed models, which creates a basis for the formation of recommendations for effective management of agricultural production.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

(Kernasiuk, (2025) examined the impact of climate change on agro-industrial production in the Kirovohrad region. It was found that under existing trends of climate change, agro-industrial production will not be able to function normally without the use of modern irrigation systems, which is due to the low amount of precipitation and its unevenness.

(Węgrzyn et al, 2022) observed winter wheat of the Turnia variety for 8 years in order to determine the relationship between individual meteorological indicators and biometric traits and winter wheat seed yield. The study showed that from the beginning of vegetative growth to the flowering stage, growth and development were fastest in plants for which the average temperature was about 8–9 °C and the number of days with precipitation was about 41. It was concluded that the weather is very variable from year to year, and therefore breeders should direct their research towards creating variants with significantly greater plasticity and high tolerance to adverse weather conditions.

(Korkhova & Mykolaichuk, 2022) investigated the degree of influence of changes in weather and climatic conditions in the main interphase periods on the growth and development and yield of durum winter wheat grain depending on the varietal composition. For six years (2014/2015-2019/2020), field studies were conducted with four durum winter wheat varieties. The study used generally accepted methods: systemic approach and systemic analysis, monographic, analysis and synthesis, field and statistical. According to the results of the research, it was determined that the formation of durum winter wheat grain yield was significantly influenced by the duration of the interphase and vegetation periods and the amount of precipitation.

(Peng et al., 2023) conducted a global meta-analysis of the relationships between climate parameters and maize yield. The results show that the effects of temperature

and precipitation on yield are nonlinear and strongly dependent on geographical conditions.

(Ehsani et al., 2022) assessed the impact of climate change on wheat yield in Egypt using CMIP6 climate scenarios and the DSSAT model. It was found that extreme temperatures and reduced precipitation could significantly reduce yield without adaptation measures.

In (Li et al., 2024) a global analysis of the impact of extreme weather events on grain yields was conducted. The authors highlight the increasing risks of crop losses due to the increase in the frequency and intensity of such events due to climate change.

(Zhang et al., 2024) analyze the spatiotemporal variability of drought effects on wheat yield on a global scale. The authors identify critical regions where yields are particularly sensitive to moisture deficits.

(Han et al., 2023) evaluated the effects of different meteorological conditions on apple yield and predicted future yield. In this study, first, the relational analysis (GRA) was used to quantitatively determine the relationship between different meteorological factors and meteorological yield, which is defined as dependent only on meteorological conditions. Then, the complex meteorological factors obtained by principal component analysis (PCA) were used as input for multiple linear regression (MLR). The accuracy of apple yield was compared with the lasso regression prediction. Trend analysis showed that the actual apple yield increased annually, but the meteorological yield decreased annually for a long time.

(Muntian, & Fedorchuk, 2023) established the influence of meteorological conditions such as temperature, precipitation and evaporation and the sum of active temperatures on the yield of winter wheat, corn and winter rapeseed using technological methods for optimizing nitrogen nutrition.

The work (Barabolia & Doronin, 2023) studied winter wheat varieties of Ukrainian selection during 2020-2022, which are characterized by high productivity, sufficient resistance to diseases and stress factors. It was determined that 2021 was the most favorable in terms of temperature and precipitation during the growing season. 2022 was the least favorable due to a prolonged cool spring, dry June and heavy precipitation in July.

In (Tereshchenko & Tarabrina, 2025) investigated the impact of classical cultivation technology and no-till technology on the efficiency of water and nutrient use, and also assessed the impact on plant resistance to extreme weather conditions. The article presented the results of the impact of no-till technology on corn and soybean yields in the conditions of the Southern Steppe of Ukraine, in particular, comparing the effectiveness with the traditional method of soil cultivation.

The study (Honcharuk & Pantsyрева, 2021) is aimed at implementing priority areas of sustainable development, namely energy efficiency and environmental safety. The monograph presents a competitive bioorganic varietal technology for growing legumes, which involves the development of regulations for the use of a complex of alternative fertilizers for their cultivation from the point of view of short-term and long-term action and the basic superstructure of factor assessment of soil fertility, environmental conditions.

In (Cheremisina & Rossokha, 2021) a comprehensive analysis of the efficiency

of grain production in Ukraine was conducted. A comprehensive analysis of the indicators of absolute and relative efficiency of grain production was conducted. A factor analysis of changes in the profitability indicators of grain production in Ukraine was conducted. The main directions for increasing the efficiency of grain production were proposed.

In (Usykova, 2023) the dynamics of changes in statistical indicators of crop production in Mykolaiv region during 1990-2021 were analyzed: gross harvest of grain and legume crops; area from which grain and legume crops were harvested; wheat yield; production of grain and legume crops per person.

In (Symonenko et al, 2024) a predictive assessment and modeling of grain and legume production in Ukraine was carried out. A comprehensive analysis of statistical data was conducted, which confirms the high adequacy of the constructed model in reflecting the relationship between independent variables, in particular, yield and area treated with mineral fertilizers.

The work (Deryng et al., 2022) is devoted to assessing the uncertainty of global and regional crop yield models under climate change. It is shown that combining several models reduces the prediction error and increases the reliability of the estimates.

(Fedorchuk et al, 2022) investigated the results of mathematical modeling of grain sorghum productivity grown in southern Ukraine under different input parameters of moisture and duration of the variety's vegetation. The regularities of grain sorghum yield formation under different influences of the studied factors and the weight of each of them in determining crop productivity were established.

The study (Mousavi et al, 2024) aimed to identify the most influential soil and environmental factors for predicting wheat yield in a part of irrigated farmland in southwestern Iran using the FAO-Agro-Climate method and machine learning (ML) algorithms. The results of this study showed that integrating simulated achievable crop growth using a crop model and a set of soil and environmental covariates with the ANN algorithm can effectively predict WY gaps over large areas with acceptable and reasonable accuracy.

(Atamanyuk et al, 2023) proposed a mathematical model based on a three-year field experiment in a semi-arid climatic zone. The novelty of this model is the inclusion of weather and technological data. The proposed method for modeling wheat yield is based on the theory of random sequence analysis. The advantage of the proposed model is the absence of restrictions on the yield function. The numerical experiment confirmed the high accuracy of the proposed mathematical model for predicting wheat yield.

(Sadenova et al, 2023) provides an overview of the accuracy of various yield prediction algorithms and offers a detailed explanation of the machine learning models and algorithms required for crop yield prediction. It is shown that the use of machine learning and neural networks for crop yield prediction has advantages over other mathematical modeling methods. The use of machine learning technologies (neural networks) allows predicting crop yields based on relevant data.

In a study (Ahmed et al, 2022), machine learning algorithms Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and Support Vector Regression (SVR) were used to predict yield

response. SVR shows better results than XGBoost for predicting yield of Aus rice ecotype, while XGBoost performs better for predicting yield of Aman and Boro rice ecotypes. In addition, this study also shows the explanatory power of the models using an artificial intelligence (XAI) model called locally interpreted model-agnostic explanations (LIME).

In (Lekakis et al, 2022) three modeling approaches based on a combination of satellite-derived vegetation indices, agrometeorological indicators and crop phenology were tested and evaluated in terms of data intensity for wheat yield prediction in large-scale applications. The results showed that the medium-input intensity methods are effective tools for yield estimation. The methods, namely: semi-empirical regression model, machine learning regression model and process model, provided high to moderate accuracy, relying entirely on freely available datasets as input sources.

An adaptive algorithm that uses correlations between time-aggregated weather variables and crop yields to predict yields has been used for forecasting major agricultural crops in Germany (Conradt, 2022). In contrast to traditional regression-based yield forecasting methods, a very wide range of possible input features and their combinations are carefully tested for maximum explanatory power. It turned out to be absolutely necessary not only to make out-of-sample forecasts (exclusively based on the data, excluding the target year for forecasting), but also to separate the training and testing years accordingly in the feature selection process. Otherwise, the forecast accuracy will be significantly overestimated.

In the work (Sarker et al., 2022) deep neural networks were used to predict rice yield under different climate scenarios. The models showed high adaptability and accuracy, which makes them promising for regions with high climate variability.

(Abiodun et al., 2024) applied machine learning algorithms to predict maize yields under climate change in African countries. The results showed that models integrated with climate scenarios can significantly improve the accuracy of forecasts and help in planning adaptive agricultural technologies.

The study (Martínez et al., 2022) demonstrates the potential for improving the accuracy of wheat yield forecasting by using satellite-derived evapotranspiration and meteorological data. The proposed approach allows for the consideration of moisture deficits at the regional level.

The study (Choudhury et al., 2023) developed an approach to forecast the yield of major cereal crops in India based on a combination of satellite data and meteorological information. The method demonstrated high accuracy and can be adapted to regional conditions in other countries.

(Feng et al., 2023) proposed a combined approach to crop yield forecasting that combines machine learning algorithms with process-oriented models. The method provided more accurate forecasts under conditions of climate variability.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, 11 independent variables were used to model yield, covering both agronomic (agrofactors) and meteorological factors (meteofactors). In particular, agrofactors included the area of grain crops (*area*), which determines the scale of cultivation and may indicate the level of agricultural intensification; the volume of

applied mineral (*minerals*), organic fertilizers (*organic*) and pesticides (*pesticides*) per 1 hectare (kg/ha) - these indicators are direct indicators of the level of agrotechnical support of crops and significantly affect the growth and development of plants, increasing yield if used in a balanced manner.

The meteorological factors included: average air temperature (*weather*) and soil surface temperature (*soil*), since thermal dynamics is one of the key factors affecting the rate of crop development and the passage of vegetation phases; precipitation (*precip*) and the number of days with precipitation (*days_prec*), which reflect not only the overall moisture content, but also the distribution of moisture during the vegetation period; average wind speed (*wind*), which can affect the processes of transpiration, moisture evaporation, as well as the spread of diseases and pollen; air moisture saturation deficit (*sat_def*) as an indicator of atmospheric dryness, which affects the water balance of plants; hydrothermal coefficient (*HTC*), which generally characterizes the ratio of moisture and heat, critical for assessing the favorableness of meteorological conditions for crop growth.

The choice of these indicators is due to their key role in the formation of the crop, which is confirmed by many previous agrometeorological and agroeconomic studies. The involvement of both agro- and meteorological factors allows for a comprehensive approach to predicting yield, taking into account both controllable (technological) and uncontrollable (natural) components of agricultural production.

The months for meteorological observations were selected as April, May, June, July, and August as the most representative for the growing season of grain crops, when the greatest impact of weather conditions on growth, development, and yield formation is observed.

One of the key meteorological indicators included in the analysis was the hydrothermal coefficient (*HTC*), which is used to assess the moisture content of an area during the growing season of agricultural crops (Chmist-Sikorska & Struzik, 2022). *HTC* is calculated using the Selyaninov formula:

$$HTC = \frac{10 \cdot \sum P}{\sum T}, \quad (1)$$

where $\sum P$ is the sum of precipitation (mm) for the period when the average daily temperature exceeds +10 °C, and $\sum T$ – is the sum of average daily air temperatures (°C) for the same period. In the calculations for the Odessa region, this coefficient was calculated by the months of vegetation (April–July), which allowed us to take into account variations in climatic conditions in the key phases of crop development: germination, tillering, earing, grain filling.

HTC values were integrated into the model as a separate feature characterizing the agroclimatic conditions of the year. This approach allowed us to take into account not only absolute meteorological indicators (temperature and precipitation separately), but also their ratio, which is critically important for assessing the impact of moisture on yield in arid regions.

Linear regression, Ridge regression, Lasso regression, and ElasticNet regression

were used to model the dependence of grain and legume crop yields on a complex of agroclimatic and agrochemical factors.

Linear regression. The linear multiple regression formula has the form (Li, 2023), (Conradt, 2022):

$$\hat{y} = \beta_0 + \sum_i \beta_i x_i, \quad (2)$$

where \hat{y} – predicted yield, β_0 – free term, β_i – coefficients for traits, x_i – values of independent variables (agro- and meteorological factors).

The variance inflation factor (VIF) was used to diagnose multicollinearity between predictors (O'Brien, 2007), (Kutner et al, 2004):

$$\text{VIF}_j = \frac{1}{1 - R_j^2}. \quad (3)$$

Here VIF_j is the variance inflation coefficient for the variable X_j , R_j^2 is the coefficient of determination when regressing the variable on all other independent variables:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{\text{res}}}{SS_{\text{tot}}}, \quad (4)$$

where $SS_{\text{res}} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$ is residual sum of squares, $SS_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2$ is residual sum of squares, y_i – actual values of the target variable, \hat{y}_i – predicted values, \bar{y} – average value y_i .

Unlike classical linear regression, Ridge regression ensures the stability of coefficient estimates thanks to L2 regularization, Lasso regression selects significant variables using L1 regularization, and Elastic Net combines both approaches, ensuring both stability and variable selection with flexible adjustment of regularization parameters.

Ridge regression. Ridge minimizes the following loss function (Hoerl, & Kennard, 1970):

$$\text{Loss} = \sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + \alpha \sum_j \beta_j^2, \quad (5)$$

where y_i is actual values of the target variable, \hat{y}_i is predicted values, β_j is model coefficients, α – regularization hyperparameter.

In this study, the model was built at $\alpha=20$.

Lasso regression minimizes the loss function (Tibshirani, 1996):

$$\text{Loss} = \sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + \alpha \sum_j |\beta_j|, \quad (6)$$

where y_i is actual values of the target variable, \hat{y}_i is predicted values, β_j is model coefficients, α – regularization hyperparameter.

Calculations were performed at $\alpha=0.55$.

ElasticNet regression is a regularized linear regression method that combines the properties of Lasso (L1-regularization) and Ridge (L2-regularization) within a single model (James et al, 2021), (Zou, & Hastie, 2005).

$$\text{Loss} = \sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + \alpha \left[\lambda \sum_j |\beta_j| + (1 - \lambda) \sum_j \beta_j^2 \right], \quad (7)$$

where α is general regularization parameter, $\lambda \in [0;1]$ – balance between L1 (Lasso) and L2 (Ridge), L1 promotes zeroing (feature selection), L2 promotes smoothing (colinearity control).

Taking into account the results of cross-validation, optimal values were achieved at $\alpha=0.41$, $\lambda=0.1$.

4. RESULTS

Let us consider the dynamics of grain and legume crop yields in the Odessa region from 1995 to 2024 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of changes in the yield of grain and leguminous crops in the Odessa region from 1995 to 2024.

Source: authors' elaboration from (State Statistics Service of Ukraine. Main Department of Statistics in Odesa Region, n.d.)

Figure 1 shows the dynamics of grain and leguminous crop yields in the Odessa region from 1995 to 2024 (in centers per hectare). Despite significant fluctuations, there is a general trend towards an increase in yields over time. If in the mid-1990s, yields often did not exceed 25 c/ha, then after 2015 most indicators are above this level, in some places exceeding 35–40 c/ha. Sharp fluctuations in yields from year to year indicate a dependence on weather conditions, the impact of droughts, changes in agricultural technologies or economic factors. The highest peak is visible in 2021 – over 40 c/ha. This is the result of favorable climatic conditions and more efficient cultivation methods. Some years, in particular 2003, 2007, 2012 and 2021, show a sharp decrease in yield, which is probably associated with climatic anomalies (Meteorological observation tables, Boris Sresnevsky central geophysical observatory, n.d). From 2020 to 2024, the yield fluctuated, but remained at a relatively high level, despite possible economic and social difficulties, including military operations in Ukraine. In general, it can be concluded that the yield of grain and leguminous crops in the Odessa region tends to increase, although it is subject to significant fluctuations. This emphasizes the need to adapt agricultural technologies to climate change and increase the resilience of agriculture to risks.

Table 1 shows the correlation of yield with agro- and meteorological factors used in the study.

Table 1

Correlation between the yield of grain and legume crops in the Odessa region and agro- and meteorological factors in the period from 1995 to 2024

<i>gather</i>	0.53	0.49	0.42	0.42	0.33	0.29	-0.05	-0.16	-0.37	-0.42	-0.46
	<i>area</i>	<i>minerals</i>	<i>pesticides</i>	<i>precip</i>	<i>HTC</i>	<i>days_prec</i>	<i>soil</i>	<i>weather</i>	<i>organics</i>	<i>sat_def</i>	<i>wind</i>

Source: authors' elaboration

Table 1 shows that the correlation coefficient between sown area (*area*) and yield (*gather*) is the highest of all factors and is equal to 0.53 (moderate positive correlation). This means that there is a certain relationship between sown area and yield: with increasing area, yield tends to increase. This may be a consequence of both the choice of more fertile lands for large-scale cultivation of crops and the use of better agrotechnical practices on large areas (modern technology, irrigation systems); The use of mineral fertilizers has a positive effect on yield (0.49): they improve photosynthesis and the formation of generative organs (grains, fruits), increase growth rates and biomass. The use of pesticides (herbicides, insecticides, fungicides) (0.42) protects crops from pests, diseases and weeds and reduces crop losses during critical growth phases. The hydrothermal coefficient (0.33) has a moderate positive effect – the optimal combination of heat and moisture promotes crop growth. The total number of days with precipitation has a weak positive correlation with yield (0.29) (more days with precipitation can be beneficial if they are uniform).

Wind (-0.46) and air moisture deficiency (-0.42) are the most harmful meteorological factors. Strong winds contribute to the drying of the soil and the evaporation of moisture from the leaves, can complicate pollination, especially during the flowering period, cause erosion and degradation of the upper soil layer. Dryness reduces yield due to plant stress.

The strongest positive factors: *area*, *minerals*, *pesticides* – these are agrofactors that are subject to regulation by agrotechnologies. The strongest negative factors: *wind*, *sat_def* – meteorological factors that objectively limit yield. The influence of *HTC* is indicative – it accumulates weather conditions and correlates well with yield.

Table 2

Coefficients of inflation of variance

Variable	<i>wind</i>	<i>area</i>	<i>HTC</i>	<i>precip</i>	<i>days_prec</i>	<i>pesticides</i>	<i>weather</i>	<i>organic</i>	<i>sat_def</i>	<i>soil</i>	<i>minerals</i>
VIF	2.05	3.11	4.24	5.11	5.95	6.25	7.13	7.17	8.84	10.67	11.09

Source: authors' elaboration

Table 2 analyzes the variance inflation coefficients (VIF) for the presence of multicollinearity between some independent variables, in particular, high values are observed for such features as *minerals*, *soil* and *sat_def*, which exceed the generally accepted threshold of 5. This indicates the potential instability of estimates within the framework of classical linear regression. The specified threshold of VIF=5 is considered in the literature as critical for detecting multicollinearity (Choueiry, n.d.). Given these results, to increase the reliability of modeling, it is advisable to also use models with regularization - Ridge, Lasso and ElasticNet, which allow reducing the influence of multicollinear features by imposing penalties on their coefficients.

Table 3

Comparison of the effectiveness of linear regression models and models with regularization

	<i>Linear Regression</i>	<i>Ridge</i>	<i>Lasso</i>	<i>ElasticNet</i>
R^2	0.257	0.606	0.581	0.587
<i>RMSE</i>	5.439	4.464	4.605	4.574
<i>MAE</i>	4.508	3.719	3.972	3.884

Source: authors' elaboration

Table 3 clearly shows that regression models with regularization (Ridge, Lasso,

ElasticNet) demonstrated significantly better accuracy compared to conventional linear regression. The highest coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.606$) and the lowest errors ($RMSE=4.46$; $MAE=3.72$) were shown by the Ridge model, which indicates its effectiveness in the presence of multicollinearity among the features.

The Lasso model was somewhat inferior in accuracy, but provided a simplification of the model - it zeroed 5 coefficients out of 11 predictors (*days_precip*, *soil*, *weather*, *HTC*, *organic*), which facilitates interpretability. The ElasticNet model combined the advantages of L1- and L2-regularization: it retained good forecast quality ($R^2=0.587$) and zeroed only one variable (*days_precip*), reducing the complexity of the model without significant loss of accuracy.

Let's focus on Ridge regression in more detail, since it showed the best result.

Based on the results of modeling using the Ridge regression method, the following equation was obtained for predicting grain yield:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{grain} = & 27.3 + 1.46 \times \text{area} + 1.02 \times \text{precip} + 0.98 \times \text{minerals} \\
 & + 0.97 \times \text{pesticides} + 0.87 \times \text{HTC} - 0.09 \text{soil} - 0.13 \times \text{weather} \\
 & - 0.19 \times \text{days_prec} - 0.22 \times \text{organic} - 1.17 \times \text{wind} - 1.209 \times \text{sat_def}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Positive values of the coefficients (*area*, *precip*, *HTC*, *minerals*, *pesticides*) indicate a favorable effect of the corresponding factors on yield, while negative coefficients (*sat_def*, *wind*, *weather*) indicate a negative effect. The selected value of the regularization parameter $\alpha=20.565$ allowed to reduce the variation of the coefficients and increase the stability of the model in conditions of multicollinearity between the predictors.

Figure 2. Importance of factors in Ridge regression.

Source: authors' elaboration

Figure 2 shows the influence of the coefficients of the Ridge regression model. The greatest positive influence on yield is exerted by the area of crops, the amount of precipitation, the amount of mineral fertilizers and pesticides applied, and the hydrothermal coefficient. In contrast, the most pronounced negative influence is observed for the saturation deficit and wind speed, which indicates a decrease in yield under arid and windy climate conditions.

Figure 3. Confidence intervals (95%) for Ridge regression coefficients.

Source: authors' elaboration

Figure 3 shows the coefficients of the Ridge regression model with 95% confidence intervals for each of the predictors. The red dashed vertical line indicates the zero value of the coefficient, which corresponds to the absence of the effect of the variable on the target (yield). The blue dots are the estimates of the model coefficients. The gray horizontal segments are the 95% confidence intervals. If the confidence interval does not cross zero, the effect of the variable can be considered statistically significant. *Area*, *precip*, *minerals*, *pesticides*, *HTC* have intervals that mostly do not cover zero, which indicates a significant effect on yield. Positive coefficients (*area*, *precip*, *minerals*, *pesticides*, *HTC*) indicate a direct relationship with the increase in yield. Negative ones (*sat_def*, *wind*, partially *organic*) indicate an inverse effect. *Area* has the largest positive effect, and *sat_def* has the largest negative effect.

Figure 4a). Dependence of grain and legume crop yields (c/ha) on the area of crops (thousand ha) in the Odessa region in the period from 1995 to 2024.

Figure 4b). Dependence of grain and legume crop yields (c/ha) on air saturation deficit (mbar) in the Odessa region in the period from 1995 to 2024

Source: authors' elaboration

In Figures 4, two scatter plots are presented, illustrating the relationship between the target variable *gather* (yield, in c/ha) and two different independent variables: *area* and *sat_def*.

In Figure 4a), a clear positive linear relationship is observed: as the sown area increases, the average yield rises. The regression line (orange) has a positive slope, which is consistent with the results of the Ridge regression model. The confidence interval (yellow area) is relatively narrow at the midrange values and wider at the extremes, indicating greater uncertainty for extreme values of the sown area.

In Figure 4b), a clear negative relationship can be observed: as the saturation deficit increases, yield decreases. The regression line (green) has a negative slope, which is consistent with the results of the Ridge regression model. The confidence interval (green area) indicates greater uncertainty of the effect at higher saturation deficit values, which may be due to a smaller number of observations in this range.

The obtained graphs confirm that an increase in the area of crops is a favorable factor for yield, while an increased saturation deficit negatively affects it, probably due to a deterioration in the water regime of plants.

5. DISCUSSION

Analysis of the coefficients of the Ridge regression model with 95% confidence intervals showed a different nature and strength of the influence of agrometeorological factors on the yield of grain and legume crops (Figure 3). The most pronounced positive effect is observed for *area* (sowing area) and *precip* (precipitation), which indicates their key role in the formation of yield. The application of mineral fertilizers (*minerals*) and pesticides (*pesticides*), as well as the hydrothermal coefficient (*HTC*)

also have a positive effect, although less pronounced.

A negative effect is found for *sat_def* (saturation deficit) and *wind* (wind speed), which may be associated with increased moisture evaporation and deterioration of crop growth conditions. A partially negative effect is also observed for *organic* (organic fertilizers), which may be due to the peculiarities of application technologies or interaction with other factors. For variables whose confidence intervals do not cover zero, the effect can be considered statistically significant (*area*, *precip*, *minerals*, *pesticides*, *HTC*).

Additional pairwise analysis (Figure 4) confirms these results. A clear positive linear relationship was found between yield (*gather*) and crop area (*area*): with an increase in crop area, the average yield increases (Figure 4a). In contrast, a pronounced negative relationship is observed for saturation deficit (*sat_def*): an increase in this indicator is accompanied by a decrease in yield (Figure 4b), probably due to a deterioration in the water regime of plants.

Thus, the results of Ridge regression and visual data analysis consistently indicate that the main positive factors of yield are the area of crop and the amount of precipitation, while the saturation deficit and strong wind have a predominantly negative impact.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study showed that the use of regularized regression methods (Ridge, Lasso, ElasticNet) allows to significantly increase the accuracy of forecasting the yield of grain and legume crops in the Odessa region compared to classical linear regression. The best results were demonstrated by the Ridge model ($R^2=0.606$; $RMSE=4.46$), which ensured the stability of coefficients in the presence of multicollinearity and high interpretability of the influence of factors.

It was found that the key positive factors of yield are the area of crops, the amount of precipitation, the application of mineral fertilizers and pesticides, as well as the hydrothermal coefficient. The negative impact is caused by the deficit of air saturation with moisture and wind speed, which reduce yield due to the deterioration of the water regime of plants and an increase in the risk of stress conditions.

Visualization of the results and pairwise analysis confirmed the identified dependencies: an increase in the area of crops correlates with an increase in yield, while a high saturation deficit causes its decrease.

The results obtained can be used to develop recommendations for optimizing agrotechnical measures, selecting adaptive varieties, and managing risks in the face of climate change. Further research should be directed towards integrating more detailed soil indicators, applying machine learning algorithms, and taking into account the spatial heterogeneity of agricultural landscapes.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study has several limitations that should be considered.

First, the analysis is based on aggregated annual data for the Odessa region, which does not fully reflect the spatial variability of soil fertility, relief, and microclimatic conditions. The use of averaged regional indicators smoothes out intra-regional

differences that can significantly affect the accuracy of yield modeling.

Secondly, the applied models (Ridge, Lasso, ElasticNet) are focused on detecting linear relationships between variables. Despite the effective consideration of multicollinearity and increased forecast accuracy, these methods may not fully reflect nonlinear relationships or threshold effects that manifest themselves under extreme weather conditions.

In further research, it is advisable to expand the analytical base by using spatially detailed data, in particular satellite indicators of vegetation, soil moisture and other agroclimatic parameters. The use of an ensemble of machine learning methods will allow better modeling of complex nonlinear relationships and increase the robustness of forecasts.

Also, a promising direction for further work is the integration of socio-economic variables – the level of investment, technological support, farm management practices – for a comprehensive assessment of yield factors. Expanding the study to other regions of Ukraine and checking the interregional transferability of models will contribute to the formation of a unified system of agricultural forecasting and adaptation of agriculture to climate risks.

Funding: The research was carried out as parts of the R&D project as follows: (0123U101895) Mathematical methods and models in applied economic research.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Abiodun, B. J., Salami, A. T., et al. (2024). Machine learning-based prediction of maize yield under changing climate in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Agricultural Systems*, 215, 103755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103755>
2. Ahmed, M. S., Tazwar, M. T., Khan, H., Roy, S., Iqbal, J., Rabiul Alam, M. G., ... & Hassan, M. M. (2022). Yield Response of Different Rice Ecotypes to Meteorological, Agro-Chemical, and Soil Physiographic Factors for Interpretable Precision Agriculture Using Extreme Gradient Boosting and Support Vector Regression. *Complexity*, 2022(1), 5305353. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5305353>
3. Atamanyuk, I., Havrysh, V., Nitsenko, V., Diachenko, O., Tepliuk, M., Chebakova, T., & Trofimova, H. (2023). Forecasting of Winter Wheat Yield: A Mathematical Model and Field Experiments. *Agriculture*, 13(1), 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13010041>
4. Barabolia, O., & Doronin, S. (2023). Influence of weather conditions and fertilizer systems on the winter wheat yield. *Scientific Progress & Innovations*, 26(1), 24–30. <https://doi.org/10.31210/spi2023.26.01.04>
5. Boris Sresnevsky central geophysical observatory. Retrieved from: <http://cgo-sresnevskiy.kyiv.ua/uk/diialnist/klimatolohichna/klimatychni-danni-po-ukraini>
6. Cheremisina, S. H., & Rossokha, V. V. (2021). Efficiency of grain production in Ukraine: analysis of the current state and prospects for improvement. *Ekonomika APK*, 6, 54-67. <https://doi.org/10.32317/2221-1055.202106054>

7. Chmista-Sikorska, J., & Struzik, P. (2022). Agricultural drought assessment on the base of Hydro-thermal Coefficient of Selyaninov in Poland. *Italian Journal of Agrometeorology*, (1), 3-12. <https://doi.org/10.36253/ijam-1530>
8. Choudhury, S., Srivastava, A. K., et al. (2023). Integrating satellite remote sensing and climate data for yield prediction of major cereal crops in India. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 209, 107848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2023.107848>
9. Choueiry, G. (n.d.). *What is a good VIF value?* Quantifying Health. Retrieved from <https://quantifyinghealth.com/vif-threshold/>
10. Conradt, T. (2022). Choosing multiple linear regressions for weather-based crop yield prediction with ABSOLUT v1. 2 applied to the districts of Germany. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 66(11), 2287-2300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-022-02356-5>
11. Deryng, D., Elliott, J., et al. (2022). Assessing uncertainty in global and regional crop model projections under climate change. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(9), 094040. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac8d91>
12. Ehsani, M., Abouhadid, A. F., et al. (2022). Climate change impact assessment on wheat yield using CMIP6 climate scenarios and DSSAT model in Egypt. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 317, 108897. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2022.108897>
13. Fedorchuk, M., Lykhovyd, P., Fedorchuk, V., Kovalenko, O., Gamayunova, V., & Khonenko, L. (2022). Mathematical model of grain sorghum yield depending on wetting conditions and variety in the south of Ukraine. *Technical and technological aspects of development and testing of new machinery and technologies for agriculture of Ukraine*, 31 (45), 130-136. [http://dx.doi.org/10.31473/2305-5987-2022-2-31\(45\)-12](http://dx.doi.org/10.31473/2305-5987-2022-2-31(45)-12)
14. Feng, P., Wang, B., et al. (2023). Combining machine learning and process-based models for improved crop yield prediction under climate variability. *Field Crops Research*, 295, 108887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2023.108887>
15. Han, X., Chang, L., Wang, N., Kong, W., & Wang, C. (2023). Effects of Meteorological Factors on Apple Yield Based on Multilinear Regression Analysis: A Case Study of Yantai Area, China. *Atmosphere*, 14(1), 183. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos14010183>
16. Hoerl, A. E., & Kennard, R. W. (1970). Ridge regression: Biased estimation for nonorthogonal problems. *Technometrics*, 12(1), 55–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.1970.10488634>
17. Honcharuk, I., & Pantsyрева, H. (2021). Efficiency of growing legumes crops in Ukraine. *Integration of traditional and innovation processes of development of modern science: collective monograph. Latvia: Riga, 2020. P. 42-65.* <https://doi.org/10.30525/978-9934-26-021-6-31>
18. James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2021). *An introduction to statistical learning* (2nd ed.). Springer.

19. Kernasiuk, Yu. (2025). The impact of climate change on agro-industrial production in the Kirovohrad region. *bulletin of Agricultural Science*, 103(1), 65-74. <https://doi.org/10.31073/agrovisnyk202501-09>
20. Korkhova, M., & Mykolaichuk, V. (2022). Influence of weather conditions on the duration of interphysical periods and yield of durum winter wheat. *Scientific Horizons*, 25(2), 36-46.
21. Kutner, M. H., Nachtsheim, C. J., & Neter, J. (2004). *Applied linear regression models* (4th ed.). McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
22. Lekakis, E., Zaikos, A., Polychronidis, A., Efthimiou, C., Pourikas, I., & Mamouka, T. (2022). Evaluation of Different Modelling Techniques with Fusion of Satellite, Soil and Agro-Meteorological Data for the Assessment of Durum Wheat Yield under a Large Scale Application. *Agriculture*, 12(10), 1635. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12101635>
23. Li, J. (2023). Multiple regression analysis of factors influencing grain yield. *Comput. Perform. Commun. Syst*, 7, 45-55. <http://dx.doi.org/10.23977/cpcs.2023.070106>
24. Li, Y., Xie, Y., et al. (2024). Effects of extreme weather events on global cereal production: A comprehensive analysis. *Nature Food*, 5, 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-023-00894-2>
25. Martínez, E., Rodríguez, D., et al. (2022). Enhancing wheat yield prediction using remote sensing-based evapotranspiration and weather data. *Agricultural Water Management*, 260, 107341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2021.107341>
26. Mousavi SR, Jahandideh Mahjenabadi VA, Khoshru B and Rezaei M (2024) Spatial prediction of winter wheat yield gap: agro-climatic model and machine learning approaches. *Front. Plant Sci.* 14:1309171. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1309171>
27. Muntian, S, & Fedorchuk, M. (2023). Impact of meteorological conditions on yield of winter wheat, maize and winter oil seed rape with using nitrification inhibitor with combined application with UAN-32. *Agrarian innovations*, (21), 64-69. <https://doi.org/10.32848/agrar.innov.2023.21.9>
28. O'Brien, R. M. (2007). A caution regarding rules of thumb for variance inflation factors. *Quality & Quantity*, 41(5), 673–690. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-006-9018-6>
29. Peng, J., Sun, Z., et al. (2023). Understanding climate-yield relationships in maize: A global meta-analysis. *Science of the Total Environment*, 857, 159525. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159525>
30. Sadenova, M., Beisekenov, N., Varbanov, P. S., & Pan, T. (2023). Application of Machine Learning and Neural Networks to Predict the Yield of Cereals, Legumes, Oilseeds and Forage Crops in Kazakhstan. *Agriculture*, 13(6), 1195. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13061195>

31. Sarker, S., Rahman, M., et al. (2022). Application of deep learning models for yield prediction of rice under different climate scenarios. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 202, 117344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.117344>
32. Symonenko, O., Huz, M., & Chukhlib, A. (2024). Modeling of the production of cereals and legumes in Ukraine: forecast assessment. *Academic Visions*, (35). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13981028>
33. Meteorological observation tables – 84. Lyubashivka, 1995–2024 // Sectoral State Archive of Hydrometeorological Observation Materials of the State Emergency Service of Ukraine. – Kyiv, 2025. – 250p.
34. Tereshchenko, A., & Tarabrina, A.-M. (2025). Performance of grain and leguminous crops under resource saving cultivation technology in the Southern Steppe of Ukraine. *Ukrainian Black Sea Region Agrarian Science*, 29(1), 72-83. <https://dspace.mnau.edu.ua/jspui/handle/123456789/21102>
35. Tibshirani, R. (1996). Regression Shrinkage and Selection via the Lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 58(1), 267–288. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1996.tb02080.x>
36. Usykova O. (2023) Economic and Statistical Analysis of Crop Production: a Regional Aspect. *Modern Economics*. 41(2023), 136-140. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.31521/modecon.V41\(2023\)-19](https://doi.org/10.31521/modecon.V41(2023)-19).
37. State Statistics Service of Ukraine. Main Department of Statistics in Odesa Region. Retrieved from: https://od.ukrstat.gov.ua/stat_info/sx/sx5.htm
38. Węgrzyn, A., Klimek-Kopyra, A., Dacewicz, E., Skowera, B., Grygierzec, W., Kulig, B., & Flis-Olszewska, E. (2022). Effect of Selected Meteorological Factors on the Growth Rate and Seed Yield of Winter Wheat—A Case Study. *Agronomy*, 12(12), 2924. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12122924>
39. Zhang, T., Chen, Y., et al. (2024). Spatiotemporal variability of drought impacts on global wheat yield. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 340, 109685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2024.109685>
40. Zou, H., & Hastie, T. (2005). Regularization and variable selection via the Elastic Net. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Statistical Methodology)*, 67(2), 301–320. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9868.2005.00503.x>